

ELIXIR Training Platform 2024 Face-to-face Meeting Report

Training Platform Leadership

Background

[ELIXIR](#) stands as a collaborative intergovernmental entity, uniting a multitude of life science resources from across Europe. Its operational framework comprises five areas, aptly referred to as [Platforms](#): Compute, Data, Interoperability, Tools, and Training. Each Platform convenes face-to-face and remotely at an annual meeting. This gathering serves as an opportunity to disseminate updates, foster insightful discussions, and collectively shape strategies that steer the current and future of the Platform. The Training Platform held this year's annual meeting in early March 2024 in Prague, Czech Republic.

Event format and participation

The ELIXIR Training Platform 2024 face-to-face meeting took place on March 4th-5th at Panorama Hotel, Prague in a hybrid format. 26 Training Platform members travelled and attended in-person, while 5 people were consistently participating remotely as the set up allowed for a hybrid experience. The event was chaired by the Training Platform Leadership, consisting of the Executive Committee members: Jessica Lindvall (ELIXIR-SE), Fotis Psomopoulos (ELIXIR-GR), and Eva Alloza (ELIXIR-ES).

Event content

The event commenced with a roundtable introduction, proceeding with an overview of the Platform's early progress in the newly-commenced [2024-26 Work Plan](#), with work package leads sharing updates and highlighting key upcoming activities under the coordination activities of Work Package 1. In Work Package 2, where the purpose is to further strengthen the infrastructure needed by the Training Platform, one discussion point of particular relevance was the continued reliance on GitHub as part of the infrastructure development. The discussions in Work Package 3 were centred on learning paths - a topic with history in the Platform, which has seen development through several [BioHackathon Europe](#) proposals. Lastly, in Work Package 4, Platform members highlighted the multiple connections that can be established between the development of training materials for the Train-the-Trainer project, such as the [FAIR Training Focus Group](#) and the [Training Metrics Database](#).

Next, the Train-the-Trainer project was discussed in detail, as supported by [Work Package 4 in the current Commissioned Service](#), its connections with the Nodes and People Tiers of the [ELIXIR Scientific Programme](#), and the synergies it has with the [ELIXIR-STEERS project](#) and [ELITMa](#).

The first day concluded with an overview of the Training Platform's engagement in Focus Groups and other regular online meetings, irrespective of connection to funded activities. Having allowed discussions to continue over the joint dinner, strategies on how to take these forward with the support and engagement of the members of the Training Platform were proposed at the start of the second day.

Date: 07/10/2024

The following day continued the topic on Focus Groups. One of the immediately actionable items of this discussion session was to revisit the liaison list - those Training Platform members who maintain connections with other groups, within and outside ELIXIR. As the discussions continued with increased focus on funding, another aspect of the role of the liaison is the envisioned facilitation towards the [Science Tier Open Call](#).

The last session of the meeting was dedicated to projects under the European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)), and the funding these facilitate. One such example is the [EOSC-OSCARS project](#), with an overview being provided by Jonathan Tedds. The Platform members were engaged and encouraged to participate representing Training activities. Another important discussion topic was to reflect on the recognition aspects of training, as previously covered during the [EOSC Winter School](#), and how the ELIXIR Training Platform can place itself to meet the challenges presented.

Outcomes and conclusion

The event has facilitated the onboarding of new Platform members by establishing personal connections, and allowed for strategic discussions about the future developments of each work package. Furthermore, the Platform members have comprehensively discussed funding opportunities and how to engage in proposals. The feedback for the event was positive from both onsite and online participants, especially regarding the increased clarity about the members' involvement in the coming 6-12 months.